

EWA-BELT

Linking East and West African farming systems experience
into a BELT of sustainable intensification

Immobilized sodium metabisulphite food grade preservative bags with a slow release of sulphur dioxide to control mycotoxins in stored legumes and cereals.

Practice Abstract n.4

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Cranfield University (CRAN), in collaboration with African partners based in Kenya and Tanzania, led research on post-harvest strategies to control mycotoxins in stored crops. The study focused on the use of food-grade sodium metabisulphite (NaMBS) bags, which slowly release sulphur dioxide (SO₂). NaMBS is commonly used as a post-harvest antifungal treatment for table grapes, effectively controlling fungal spoilage caused by *Botrytis cinerea* (grey mould) during storage. This research explored the adaptation of NaMBS pads, designed to gradually release SO₂, into 3 kg capacity storage bags as a potential strategy for preventing fungal spoilage and mycotoxin production in various crops. Lab tests on unshelled peanuts under dry (0.85 aw[1]) and wet (0.95 aw) conditions showed SO₂ bags completely inhibited fungal growth in naturally contaminated peanuts, while reducing fungal loads by 72% and 49% in *A. flavus*-inoculated peanuts at 0.85 and 0.95 aw, respectively. Aflatoxin B₁ (AFB₁) was also inhibited. Further trials on shelled peanuts at 0.85 (dry), 0.90 (relatively dry), and 0.95 (wet) aw over 21 days showed a 45% fungal reduction when peanuts were stored in SO₂-releasing bags at 0.90 aw. AFB₁ was undetectable at 0.85 and 0.90 aw, while at 0.95 aw, it was reduced 10-fold compared to peanuts kept in plastic bags (control conditions). Ongoing trials by KALRO and the University of Nairobi (Kenya) and NM-AIST (Tanzania) are evaluating SO₂ bags for safe storage of finger millet, maize, sorghum, and peanuts at 13%, 15%, 17% and 20% (from slightly high to unsafe) moisture content, compared with gunny and hermetic PICS bags over six months. Findings confirm SO₂ bags effectively reduce fungal spoilage and mycotoxin contamination, especially in moderately dry conditions. Future research should optimise scalability for widespread adoption in smallholder systems.

[1] Aw: "free water" or "water activity". Free water or the water activity level is the amount of water not bound with other non-water molecules. Since unbonded water supports the growth of microorganisms, the stability or shelf life of food is partially determined by the amount of free water in a product. It is the ratio of a product's vapor pressure to the vapor pressure of distilled or pure water, that it is equal to 1.

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